

Supplementary Material

Asymptotic beam theory for non-classical elastic materials and its general analytical solution

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1 Some expressions that arise in the iterative procedure

Displacement expansion coefficients are:

$$\begin{aligned}u_1^{(0)i} &= 2\lambda_2 \int_0^x \exp\left(\eta(T_{11}^{(0)i}(\xi) - q_2^-)\right) T_{11}^{(0)i}(\xi) d\xi + \lambda_1 \left(\frac{h^2}{3} \int_0^x T_{11}^{(2)i}(\xi) d\xi - q_2^- x + C_3^i x \right. \\ &\quad \left. - \frac{\bar{q}_1 x^2}{2} + \frac{3mx^2}{2h} + \frac{\bar{q}_2 x^3}{2h} - \frac{C_1^i h x^2}{2} - C_2^i h x + C_4^i \right), \\ u_1^{(1)i} &= 2\lambda_2 \int_0^x \exp\left(\eta(T_{11}^{(0)i}(\xi) - q_2^-)\right) T_{11}^{(1)i}(\xi) d\xi + \lambda_1 \left(-\frac{3mx^2}{2h^2} - \frac{\bar{q}_2 x^3}{2h^2} + \frac{C_1^i x^2}{2} - h \right. \\ &\quad \left. \int_0^x T_{11}^{(2)i} d\xi + C_2^i x \right) + C_5^i + 2\lambda_2 \eta \int_0^x \exp\left(\eta(T_{11}^{(0)i}(\xi) - q_2^-)\right) T_{11}^{(0)i}(\xi) T_{11}^{(1)i}(\xi) d\xi, \\ u_1^{(2)i} &= 2\lambda_2 q_2^- \eta T_{12}^{(1)i} \exp\left(\eta(T_{11}^{(0)i} - q_2^-)\right) + \lambda_1 T_{12}^{(1)i} + 4\lambda_2 \exp\left(\eta(T_{11}^{(0)i} - q_2^-)\right) T_{12}^{(1)i} - \\ &\quad 4\lambda_2 \eta q_1^- \exp\left(\eta(T_{11}^{(0)i} - q_2^-)\right) T_{11}^{(1)i}, \\ u_2^{(0)i} &= 2\lambda_2 \int_0^x (\xi - x) \exp\left(\eta(T_{11}^{(0)i}(\xi) - q_2^-)\right) T_{11}^{(1)i}(\xi) d\xi - 4\lambda_2 q_1^- \int_0^x \exp\left(\eta(T_{11}^{(0)i}(\xi) \right. \\ &\quad \left. - q_2^-)\right) d\xi - \lambda_1 \left(-\frac{mx^3}{2h^2} + \frac{C_1^i x^3}{6} + \frac{C_2^i x^2}{2} - h \int_0^x (x - \xi) T_{11}^{(2)i}(\xi) d\xi \right) - 2\lambda_2 \eta \int_0^x (x - \\ &\quad \xi) \exp\left(\eta(T_{11}^{(0)i}(\xi) - q_2^-)\right) T_{11}^{(0)i}(\xi) T_{11}^{(1)i}(\xi) d\xi + \lambda_1 \frac{\bar{q}_2 x^4}{8h^2} - C_5^i x + C_6^i,\end{aligned}$$

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$$u_2^{(1)i} = \lambda_1(T_{11}^{(0)i} - q_2^-) - 2\lambda_2 q_2^- \exp\left(\eta(T_{11}^{(0)i} - q_2^-)\right),$$

$$T_{11}^{(2)i} = \lambda_1 T_{11}^{(1)i} - 2\lambda_2 \eta q_2^- T_{11}^{(1)i} \exp\left(\eta(T_{11}^{(0)i} - q_2^-)\right),$$

The update to $T_{11}^{(2)i+1}$ is given by

$$T_{11}^{(2)i+1} = \frac{f_{i1}(x)}{f_{i2}(x)},$$

where

$$f_{i1} = \frac{\partial u_1^{(2)i}}{\partial x} - \lambda_1 T_{22}^{(2)i} - 2\lambda_2 \eta \exp\left(\eta(T_{11}^{(0)i} - q_2^-)\right) T_{22}^{(2)i} T_{11}^{(0)i} - 2\lambda_2 \eta^2 \exp\left(\eta(T_{11}^{(0)i} - q_2^-)\right) T_{11}^{(1)i} T_{11}^{(1)i} T_{11}^{(0)i} - 4\lambda_2 \eta \exp\left(\eta(T_{11}^{(0)i} - q_2^-)\right) T_{11}^{(1)i} T_{11}^{(1)i},$$

$$f_{i2} = \lambda_1 + 2\lambda_2 \exp\left(\eta(T_{11}^{(0)i} - q_2^-)\right) + 2\lambda_2 \eta \exp\left(\eta(T_{11}^{(0)i} - q_2^-)\right) T_{11}^{(0)i}.$$

Ending criteria for the iteration procedure are:

$$\frac{h|T_{11}^{(2)i+1} - T_{11}^{(2)i}|_{max}}{|T_{11}^{(1)i}|_{max}} < \mu \text{ and } \frac{h^2|T_{11}^{(2)i+1} - T_{11}^{(2)i}|_{max}}{3|T_{11}^{(0)i}|_{max}} < \mu, \quad (1)$$

for a chosen small μ .

For the first example, three integration constants (for $i = 2$) are:

$$C_4 = -\lambda_1 \left(C_3 L - \frac{C_1 h L^2}{2} - C_2 h L + \frac{h^2}{3} \int_0^L T_{11}^{(2)2} dx \right) - 2\lambda_2 \int_0^L \exp\left(\eta(C_3 - C_1 h x - C_2 h + \frac{h^2}{3} T_{11}^{(2)2})\right) (C_3 - C_1 h x - C_2 h + \frac{h^2}{3} T_{11}^{(2)2}) dx - 2\lambda_2 C_1 h^3 \exp\left(\eta(C_3 - C_1 h L - C_2 h + \frac{h^2}{3} T_{11}^{(2)2}(L))\right) + (\lambda_1 + 2\lambda_2) \frac{h^4}{3} \frac{\partial T_{11}^{(2)2}}{\partial x}(L),$$

$$C_5 = -2\lambda_2 \int_0^L \exp\left(\eta(C_3 - C_1 h x - C_2 h + \frac{h^2}{3} T_{11}^{(2)2})\right) (C_1 x + C_2 - h T_{11}^{(2)2}) dx - 2\lambda_2 \eta \int_0^L \exp\left(\eta(C_3 - C_1 h x - C_2 h + \frac{h^2}{3} T_{11}^{(2)2})\right) (C_3 - C_1 h x - C_2 h + \frac{h^2}{3} T_{11}^{(2)2}) (C_1 x + C_2 - h T_{11}^{(2)2}) dx - \lambda_1 \left(\frac{C_1 L^2}{2} + C_2 L - h \int_0^L T_{11}^{(2)2} dx \right) - \lambda_1 \frac{C_1 h^2}{2} - \lambda_1 \frac{h^3}{6} \frac{\partial T_{11}^{(2)2}}{\partial x}(L),$$

$$C_6 = -2\lambda_2 \int_0^L x \exp\left(\eta(C_3 - C_1 h x - C_2 h + \frac{h^2}{3} T_{11}^{(2)2})\right) (C_1 x + C_2 - h T_{11}^{(2)2}) dx - 2\lambda_2 \eta \int_0^L x \exp\left(\eta(C_3 - C_1 h x - C_2 h + \frac{h^2}{3} T_{11}^{(2)2})\right) (C_3 - C_1 h x - C_2 h + \frac{h^2}{3} T_{11}^{(2)2}) (C_1 x + C_2 - h T_{11}^{(2)2}) dx + \lambda_1 \left(-\frac{L h^3}{6} \frac{\partial T_{11}^{(2)2}}{\partial x}(L) + \frac{h^3}{6} T_{11}^{(2)2}(L) + \frac{C_2 h^2}{2} - C_3 h \right) + \lambda_1 \left(-\frac{C_1 L^3}{6} - \frac{C_2 L^2}{2} + h \int_0^L x T_{11}^{(2)2} d\xi \right).$$

Note: By taking $\eta = 0$, we can obtain the corresponding \hat{C}_4 , \hat{C}_5 and \hat{C}_6 for the linearized case.

For the second example, expressions for the three nonzero integrations constants in the linearized ($\eta = 0$) case are:

$$\begin{aligned}\hat{C}_2 &= \frac{q(9\lambda_1 + 24\lambda_2)}{4h(\lambda_1 + 2\lambda_2)} - \frac{qL^2}{4h^3}, \quad \hat{C}_3 = \frac{q(5\lambda_1 + 4\lambda_2)}{4(\lambda_1 + 2\lambda_2)}, \\ \hat{C}_6 &= \frac{3hq\lambda_1(\lambda_1 + 8\lambda_2)}{8(\lambda_1 + 2\lambda_2)} - \frac{q\lambda_1L^2}{8h} - \frac{q(\lambda_1 + 2\lambda_2)L^4}{16h^3}.\end{aligned}$$

2 Numerical simulations

2.1 Linearization

We need to solve the original 2D boundary value problem with specific boundary conditions. The governing equations are

$$\begin{cases} \nabla \cdot \mathbf{T} = \mathbf{0}, \\ \boldsymbol{\epsilon}(\mathbf{u}) = \lambda_1 \text{Tr}(\mathbf{T})\mathbf{I} + 2\lambda_2 \exp(\eta \text{Tr}(\mathbf{T}))\mathbf{T}, \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

which is nonlinear with respect to the mixed unknowns $\mathbf{V} = (T_{11}, T_{22}, T_{12}, u_1, u_2) = T_{11}\mathbf{E}_1 + T_{22}\mathbf{E}_2 + T_{12}\mathbf{E}_3 + u_1\mathbf{E}_4 + u_2\mathbf{E}_5$ with an orthonormal basis $\{\mathbf{E}_1, \mathbf{E}_2, \mathbf{E}_3, \mathbf{E}_4, \mathbf{E}_5\}$ (we take $\mathbf{E}_1 = \mathbf{e}_1, \mathbf{E}_2 = \mathbf{e}_2$). For ease of exposition, we introduce the vector forms for the stress and strain tensors defined respectively by $\check{\mathbf{T}} = T_{11}\mathbf{E}_1 + T_{22}\mathbf{E}_2 + T_{12}\mathbf{E}_3$ and $\check{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}} = \epsilon_{11}\mathbf{E}_3 + \epsilon_{22}\mathbf{E}_4 + \epsilon_{12}\mathbf{E}_5$. Then, $\text{Tr}(\mathbf{T}) = \check{\mathbf{T}} \cdot (\mathbf{E}_1 + \mathbf{E}_2)$. In what follows, we solve this problem numerically by using the mixed variables \mathbf{V} since the constitutive relation (??) expresses the strain tensor as a function of stress tensor. The above 2D system can be rewritten in the compact form,

$$\mathcal{L}\mathbf{V} + \mathcal{N}\mathbf{V} = \mathbf{0}, \quad (3)$$

where \mathcal{L} and \mathcal{N} are operators acting on \mathbf{V} . More specifically,

$$\begin{aligned}\mathcal{L}\mathbf{V} &= \left[\nabla \cdot ((\check{\mathbf{T}} \cdot \mathbf{E}_1)\mathbf{E}_1 + (\check{\mathbf{T}} \cdot \mathbf{E}_3)\mathbf{E}_2) \right] \mathbf{E}_1 + \left[\nabla \cdot ((\check{\mathbf{T}} \cdot \mathbf{E}_3)\mathbf{E}_1 \right. \\ &\quad \left. + (\check{\mathbf{T}} \cdot \mathbf{E}_2)\mathbf{E}_2) \right] \mathbf{E}_2 + \check{\boldsymbol{\epsilon}} - \lambda_1 [\check{\mathbf{T}} \cdot (\mathbf{E}_1 + \mathbf{E}_2)] (\mathbf{E}_3 + \mathbf{E}_4),\end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

$$\mathcal{N}\mathbf{V} = \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{V}) = -2\lambda_2 \exp[\eta(\check{\mathbf{T}} \cdot (\mathbf{E}_1 + \mathbf{E}_2))] (\check{\mathbf{T}} \cdot \mathbf{E}_i) \mathbf{E}_{i+2}, \quad (5)$$

where $i = 1, 2, 3$ and summation is in place. The first and second equations are the linear and nonlinear parts of (2), respectively.

Following this, we will apply Newton linearized method to linearize the 2D system. For the nonlinear terms appearing in (3), the iteration is of the form,

$$\mathcal{N}\mathbf{V}_n = \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{V}_{n-1}) + \mathbf{F}_v(\mathbf{V}_{n-1})(\mathbf{V}_n - \mathbf{V}_{n-1}). \quad (6)$$

Therefore, the linearized iteration form of (3) reads

$$\mathcal{L}\mathbf{V}_n + \mathbf{F}_v(\mathbf{V}_{n-1})\mathbf{V}_n = \mathbf{F}_v(\mathbf{V}_{n-1})\mathbf{V}_{n-1} - \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{V}_{n-1}), \quad (7)$$

where n is any positive integer and $\mathbf{F}_v(\mathbf{V}_{n-1})$ is the Jacobian matrix with regard to \mathbf{V} at $\mathbf{V} = \mathbf{V}_{n-1}$.

2.2 Spectral collocation method

To solve the linearized system (7), we adopt the spectral collocation method to discretize it. In view of the bounded non-periodic domain $[x, y] \in [0, L] \times [0, 2h]$, we firstly transform it into the computational domain $[\tilde{x}, \tilde{y}] \in [-1, 1] \times [-1, 1]$ and discretize the computational domain by a grid with Chebyshev-Gauss-Lobatto points. Then we can use these collocation points to construct differential matrices. Based on these considerations, we start with recalling the spectral method with Chebyshev-Gauss-Lobatto points in one dimension and the computational domain is $[-1, 1]$.

Initially, one introduces the Chebyshev-Gauss-Lobatto points through

$$x_k = \cos\left(\frac{k-1}{M-1}\pi\right), \quad k = 1, \dots, M, \quad x_k \in [-1, 1], \quad (8)$$

where M denotes the number of collocation points. To derive the differential matrices, we recall the spectral method based on the following interpolation form (see [3]):

$$f(x) \approx P_{M-1}(x) = \sum_{j=1}^M \phi_j(x) f_j, \quad f_j = f(x_j), \quad (9)$$

where $\{\phi_j | j = 1, \dots, M\}$ are the Lagrange basis polynomials associated with the set of Chebyshev-Gauss-Lobatto points $\{x_j | j = 1, \dots, M\}$ and the general form is

$$\phi_j(x) = \frac{(-1)^j}{c_j} \frac{1-x^2}{(M-1)^2} \frac{T'_{M-1}(x)}{x-x_j}, \quad (10)$$

where $T_{M-1}(x)$ is the Chebyshev polynomial of the first kind with degree $M-1$, $c_1 = c_M = 2$ and $c_2 = \dots = c_{M-1} = 1$. Hence, in order to evaluate approximately the l th derivative of $f(x)$ at the node x_k , one can differentiate (9) l times and obtain

$$f^l(x_k) \approx \sum_{j=1}^M \phi_j^{(l)}(x_k) f_j, \quad 1 \leq k \leq M. \quad (11)$$

To express the numerical differentiation (11) in a compact form, let us denote

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{f}^{(l)} &:= (f^{(l)}(x_1), \dots, f^{(l)}(x_M))^T, \quad \mathbf{f} := \mathbf{f}^{(0)}, \\ D_{kj}^{(l)} &:= \phi_j^{(l)}(x_k). \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Therefore, (11) can be rewritten as

$$\mathbf{f}^{(l)} \approx D^{(l)} \mathbf{f}. \quad (13)$$

In particular, the first-order differentiation matrix is given by [2],

$$D_{kj}^{(1)} = \begin{cases} \frac{c_k(-1)^{j+k}}{c_j(x_k-x_j)}, & j \neq k, \\ \frac{x_k}{2(x_k^2-1)}, & j = k \neq 1, M, \\ \frac{2(M-1)^2+1}{6}, & j = k = 1, \\ -\frac{2(M-1)^2+1}{6}, & j = k = M. \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

In addition, one can prove that $D^{(l)} = (D^{(1)})^l$, as shown in [3].

For a 2D grid with n_1 , n_2 Chebyshev collocation points in the x -direction and y -direction respectively, we store the value of $f(x, y)$ on the grid as a 1D array, \mathbf{f} , of size $N_{2D} = n_1 n_2$. To approximate the partial derivatives in each direction, we firstly denote the l th differentiation matrices in the two directions by $D_1^{(l)} = D_{n_1 \times n_1}^{(l)}$ and $D_2^{(l)} = D_{n_2 \times n_2}^{(l)}$. Besides, [4] provides the easiest way to construct 2D differentiation matrices acting on the 1D arrays of size N_{2D} using the Kronecker product:

$$\tilde{D}_1^{(l)} = D_1^{(l)} \otimes I_2, \quad \tilde{D}_2^{(l)} = I_1 \otimes D_2^{(l)}, \quad (15)$$

where I_α is the identity matrix of size $n_\alpha \times n_\alpha$ and $\alpha = 1, 2$. Also, $\tilde{D}^{(l)}$ denotes the 2D differentiation matrix of size $N_{2D} \times N_{2D}$. Therefore, we obtain

$$\mathbf{f}_x^{(l)} \approx \tilde{D}_1^{(l)} \mathbf{f}, \quad \mathbf{f}_y^{(l)} \approx \tilde{D}_2^{(l)} \mathbf{f}, \quad (16)$$

where $\mathbf{f}_x^{(l)}$ and $\mathbf{f}_y^{(l)}$ denote the l th partial derivatives on the grid with regard to x and y , respectively.

2.3 Numerical implementations for the two examples

To solve the linearized system (7) by the spectral collocation method, we firstly consider the the computational domain $[\tilde{x}, \tilde{y}] \in [-1, 1] \times [-1, 1]$ which is then discretized using a grid based on the Chebyshev-Gauss-Lobatto points,

$$\tilde{x}_i = \cos\left(\frac{(i-1)\pi}{M}\right), \quad i = 1, \dots, M, \quad (17)$$

$$\tilde{y}_j = \cos\left(\frac{(j-1)\pi}{N}\right), \quad j = 1, \dots, N, \quad (18)$$

where M and N denote the numbers of collocation points in the x -direction and y -direction, respectively. In both examples, we proceed by taking $M = N = 23$.

Based on (14) and (15), $D_1^{(1)}$ and $D_2^{(1)}$ can be derived directly. However, we need to transform the current computational domain into the actual physical domain $[x, y] \in [a, b] \times [c, d]$ through

$$\begin{aligned} x_i &= (b+a)/2 - (b-a)\tilde{x}_i/2, \\ y_j &= (c+d)/2 - (d-c)\tilde{y}_j/2, \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

where $a = 0$, $b = L$, $c = 0$, $d = 2h$ in the first example and $a = -L$, $b = L$, $c = 0$, $d = 2h$ in the second example. Furthermore, the corresponding differentiation matrices should be of the following forms:

$$D_1^{(1)} = -(2/(b-a))D_1^{(1)}, \quad D_2^{(1)} = -(2/(d-c))D_2^{(1)}. \quad (20)$$

Afterwards, $\tilde{D}_1^{(1)}$ and $\tilde{D}_2^{(1)}$ can be obtained using (15). The overall stiff matrix \mathbf{K} of size $5MN \times 5MN$ in (7) can thenceforth be calculated. Also, the discrete form for (7) reads

$$\mathbf{K}V_n = \mathbf{F}_v(\mathbf{V}_{n-1})\mathbf{V}_{n-1} - \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{V}_{n-1}), \quad (21)$$

Now V_n and the right hand sides of (21) represent the values at the collocation points.

Actually, \mathbf{K} is composed of five matrix blocks since (7) contains five equations. We hence denote

$$\mathbf{K} = \begin{bmatrix} K_1 \\ K_2 \\ K_3 \\ K_4 \\ K_5 \end{bmatrix}, \quad (22)$$

where \mathbf{K}_j are the matrices of size $MN * 5MN$.

After dealing with the differential equations, we now concentrate on the boundary conditions (BCs). For the first example, to satisfy the boundary conditions at $x = 0$, we take

$$T_{11} = 0, \quad T_{12} = \frac{3t_y}{2h^2}(y^2 - 2hy), \quad \text{at } x = 0, \quad (23)$$

where T_{11} and T_{12} are determined based on the exact solutions in the classical linear model. Besides, for the clamped edge $x = L$, we take

$$u_1 = 0, \quad u_2 = 0, \quad \text{at } x = L. \quad (24)$$

Then, in view of the traction-free upper and lower surfaces, the BCs are imposed by

$$\mathbf{T}\mathbf{n} = -\mathbf{q}^-, \quad \text{at } y = 0, \quad \mathbf{T}\mathbf{n} = \mathbf{q}^+, \quad \text{at } y = 2h, \quad (25)$$

where $\mathbf{q}^- = \mathbf{q}^+ = (0, 0)^\top$.

For the second example, because of two clamped edges, the BCs can be imposed through assuming

$$u_1 = u_2 = 0, \quad \text{at } x = -L, L. \quad (26)$$

Furthermore, the beam is subjected to a uniform load at the upper surface and free at the lower surface, therefore,

$$\mathbf{T}\mathbf{n} = -\mathbf{q}^-, \quad \text{at } y = 0, \quad \mathbf{T}\mathbf{n} = \mathbf{q}^+, \quad \text{at } y = 2h, \quad (27)$$

where $\mathbf{q}^- = (0, 0)^\top$ and $\mathbf{q}^+ = (0, -q)^\top$.

We notice that the BCs in these two examples are all of the Dirichlet type. Therefore, with respect to the boundary collocation points of the beam in first example, (23), (24) and (25) indicate that

$$\begin{aligned} T_{11}(0, y_l) &= 0, \quad T_{12}(0, y_l) = \frac{3t_y}{2h^2}(y_l^2 - 2hy_l), \\ T_{12}(x_g, 0) &= 0, \quad T_{12}(x_g, 2h) = 0, \quad T_{22}(x_g, 0) = 0, \\ T_{22}(x_g, 2h) &= 0, \quad u_1(L, y_l) = 0, \quad u_2(L, y_l) = 0, \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

where l, g respectively runs from 2 to $N - 1$, 1 to M .

Based on the order of the collocation points in 2D adopted by spectral collocation method(see [4]), the index set of the boundary collocation points reads

$$IS1 = \{l, N + (g - 1)N, 1 + (g - 1)N, (M - 1)N + l\}. \quad (29)$$

In addition, based on the order of the variables of V_n valued at the collocation points, the index set of the discrete boundary conditions (28) in V_n is denoted by

$$IS2 = \{(M-1)N+l, MN+(M-1)N+l, 2MN+l, 3MN+1+(g-1)N, 3MN+N+(g-1)N, 4MN+l, 4MN+1+(g-1)N, 4MN+N+(g-1)N\}. \quad (30)$$

On substituting (28) into V_n in (21), we can move the multiplication between the columns with index (30) of \mathbf{K} and the known values at the boundary collocation points to the right hand side of (21).

To solve the remaining unknowns in V_n , we need to drop the rows with index (29) of \mathbf{K}_1 and \mathbf{K}_2 to ensure that the remaining equations have the same number as the remaining unknowns. Thereby, the remaining unknowns can be determined.

With respect to the second example, we also carry out the same manipulations. For details regarding the manipulations for more complicated boundary conditions, one can refer to [1].

References

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